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Appendix A: Disciplines of Supported Projects in Year 6

Center Project

Course

Meeting

Visiting Scholar

Appendix A: Disciplines of Supported Projects in Year 6

	Center Project	Course	Meeting		Visiting Scholar				Total
			Catalysis Meeting	Working Group	Graduate Fellow	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	
Applied Evolution	0	0	2	2	0	0	2	0	6
Behavior or Neurobiology	0	0	0	2	1	0	4	2	9
Comparative Biology	1	0	3	5	1	2	6	5	23
Development	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	2	6
Education	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	3
Evolutionary Ecology or Population Biology	1	1	3	4	4	2	7	3	25
Genomics or Proteomics	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	6
Molecular Evolution	0	0	2	1	1	3	2	2	11
Paleontology	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	1	5
Phylogeography or Speciation	0	0	1	3	0	1	4	3	12
Physiology or Functional Morphology	0	0	0	2	1	1	2	2	8
Population or Evolutionary Genetics	0	0	4	3	0	3	2	2	14
Systematics or Phylogenetics	1	0	0	2	2	2	8	4	19
Other	1	1	2	2	2	1	4	4	17

Appendix B1: Gender of Project PI's and Co-PI's in Year 6

	Catalysis Meeting	Graduate Fellow	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	Working Group	Total
Female	6	1	1	4	6	11	29
Male	14	4	6	12	9	20	65
Total	20	5	7	16	15	31	94

Appendix B2: Ethnicity of Project PI's and Co-PI's in Year 6

	Catalysis Meeting	Graduate Fellow	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	Working Group	Total
Do not wish to provide	4	0	0	1	3	4	12
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	3	0	1	4
Not Hispanic or Latino	16	5	7	12	12	26	78
Total	20	5	7	16	15	31	94

Appendix B3: Race of Project PI's and Co-PI's in Year 6

	Catalysis Meeting	Graduate Fellow	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	Working Group	Total
Asian	1	0	0	0	0	1	2
Black or African	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Hispanic or Latino	0	0	0	2	0	0	2
White	13	5	7	11	12	26	74
Do not wish to provide	6	0	0	3	3	3	15
Total	20	5	7	16	15	31	94

Appendix B4: Nationality of Project PI's and Co-PI's in Year 6

	Catalysis Meeting	Graduate Fellow	Long-term Sabbatical	Postdoctoral Fellow	Short-term Visitor	Working Group	Total
Non-US Citizen	8	0	1	5	8	5	27
Permanent Resi	1	0	1	1	2	1	6
US Citizen	11	5	5	10	5	25	61
Total	20	5	7	16	15	31	94

Appendix C1: Gender of Participants in Year 6

	Catalysis Meeting	Working Group	Total
Do not wish to provide	1	8	9
Female	46	259	305
Male	204	518	722
No Answer	5	27	32
Total	256	812	1,068

Appendix C2: Ethnicity of Participants in Year 6

	Catalysis Meeting	Working Group	Total
Do not wish to provide	7	42	49
Hispanic or Latino	16	45	61
Not Hispanic or Latino	228	695	923
No Answer	5	30	35
Total	256	812	1,068

Appendix C3: Race of Participants in Year 6

	Catalysis Meeting	Working Group	Total
Do not wish to provide	66	56	122
Asian	36	24	60
Black or African American	0	28	28
White	154	694	848
No Answer	0	10	10
Total	256	812	1,068

Appendix C4: Nationality of Participants in Year 6

	Catalysis Meeting	Working Group	Total
Do not wish to provide	1	8	9
Non-US Citizen	80	158	238
Permanent Resident	10	55	65
US Citizen	160	564	724
No Answer	5	27	32
Total	256	812	1,068

Appendix D: Countries of Participant Institutions

Participants by Country

- 355 to 355 (1)
- 13 to 355 (1)
- 12 to 13 (1)
- 7 to 12 (1)
- 4 to 7 (2)
- 3 to 4 (2)
- 2 to 3 (5)
- 1 to 2 (6)

	Total
	114
ARGENTINA	4
AUSTRALIA	7
AUSTRIA	2
BELGIUM	1
CANADA	12
CHILE	1
COLOMBIA	1
DENMARK	1
FRANCE	2
GERMANY	2
IRELAND	2
NETHERLANDS	3
NEW ZEALAND	1
NOT APPLICABLE	1
SOUTH AFRICA	1
SPAIN	2
SWEDEN	3
SWITZERLAND	4
UNITED KINGDOM	13
UNITED STATES	355
Total	532

Appendix E: U.S. States of Unique Participants' Institution

Participants by State

- 91 to 91 (1)
- 14 to 91 (5)
- 8 to 14 (6)
- 6 to 8 (9)
- 4 to 6 (8)
- 3 to 4 (3)
- 2 to 3 (6)
- 1 to 2 (7)

Appendix E: U.S. States of Participant Institutions

	Total
AK	1
AZ	9
CA	32
CO	10
CT	18
DC	8
DE	1
FL	3
GA	6
HI	1
IA	4
IL	7
IN	7
KS	7
KY	2
LA	1
ma	19
MD	7
ME	3
MI	7
MN	2
MO	6
MT	3
NC	91
NE	4
NH	2
NJ	4
NM	2
NV	1
NY	21
OH	6
Ok	2
OR	8
PA	14
RI	6
SC	4
SD	2
TN	5
TX	5
UT	4
VA	9
VT	1
WA	8
WI	4
WY	1
Total	365

Appendix F: Detailed List of Activities and Participants in Year 6

Catalysis Meeting

Evolution of g protein coupled signaling: lineages, constraints, and tempo

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=204

Dates: 5/17/2010 - 5/19/2010

<u>PI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
Alan Jones	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

<u>CoPI</u>	
Etsuko Moriyama	University of Nebraska-Lincoln
Jotun Hein	Oxford University
Joe Thornton	University of Oregon

<u>Participants</u>	
John Hepler	Emory University
Stephen Lanier	Medical University of South Carolina
Joe Thornton	University of Oregon
Willie Taylor	MRC National Institute for Medical Research
Todd Vision	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Roger Sunahara	University of Michigan Medical School
Eric Gaucher	Georgia Institute of Technology
John Sondek	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Thomas Wilkie	University of Texas Southwestern Medical Center
Henrik Dohlman	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Brenda Temple	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Joel Dacks	University of Alberta
Etsuko Moriyama	University of Nebraska-Lincoln
Dagmar Iber	ETH Zurich
John Hildebrandt	Medical University of South Carolina
Andrew Roger	Dalhousie University
Laura Katz	Smith College
John M Logsdon	University of Iowa/NESCent
Jotun Hein	Oxford University
David Liberles	University of Wyoming
James Garrison	University of Virginia
Charlie Carter	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
David Robertson	University of Manchester
Stephanie Hicks	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Vsevolod Gurevich	Vanderbilt University
Alan Jones	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Integrating datasets to investigate megafaunal extinction in the late quaternary

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=205

Dates: 5/26/2010 - 5/29/2010

<u>PI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
Jessica Metcalf 2	University of Adelaide

<u>CoPI</u>	
Rob Guralnick	University of Colorado
Alan Cooper	University of Adelaide

Participants

Jessica Metcalf 2	University of Adelaide
Felisa A Smith	University of New Mexico
Beth Shapiro	Pennsylvania State University
Alan Cooper	University of Adelaide
Rob Guralnick	University of Colorado
Eric Dechaine	Western Washington University
Miguel Araujo	Spanish Research Council (CSIC)
Gary Haynes	University of Nevada-Reno
Adolfo Gil	CONICET-MUSEO DE HISTORIA NATURAL DE SAN RAFAEL
Greg McDonald	US National Park Service
Stefan Prost	Gregor Mendel Institute of Molecular Plant Biology
Christian Anderson	University of California-San Diego
Paul Baker	Duke University
Jack Williams	University of Wisconsin
Grant Zazula	Government of Yukon
Partricio Moreno	University of Chile
Julie A Meachen-Samuels	NESCent
Corey Bradshaw	University of Adelaide
Jacob Enk	McMaster University
Kristofer Helgen	Smithsonian Institution
John Stewart	Bournemouth University
Andrew Storfer	Washington State University

Working Group

Costs of phenotypic plasticity and adaptation to novel environments

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=193

Dates: 1/22/2010 - 1/24/2010

PI

Courtney Murren

Institution

College of Charleston

CoPI

Carl Schlichting

University of Connecticut

Participants

Courtney Murren	College of Charleston
Carl Schlichting	University of Connecticut
Heidi Maclean	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Mary Heskell	Columbia University
Josh R Auld	NESCent
Ulrich Steiner	Stanford University
Cameron Ghalambor	Colorado State University
Hilary Callahan	Barnard College
David Pfennig	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Heather Maughan	University of Toronto
Corey Handelsman	Colorado State University
Emilie Snell-Rood	University of Indiana-Bloomington
Joanna Masel	University of Arizona
Rick Relyea	University of Pittsburgh
Joel Kingsolver	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Sarah Seiter	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Floral assembly: quantifying the composition of a complex adaptive structure

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=90

Dates: 1/30/2010 - 2/1/2010

PI

William Scott Armbruster

Institution

University of Alaska-Fairbanks

CoPI

Participants

Stephen Smith	NESCent
Stacey D Smith	Duke University
Christopher Hardy	Millersville State University
William Scott Armbruster	University of Portsmouth
Larry Hufford	Washington State University
Amy Litt	New York Botanical Garden
Lawrence Harder	University of Calgary
Pamela K Diggle	University of Colorado
Peter Stevens	University of Missouri-St. Louis
Charles Fenster	University of Maryland-College Park
Lena C Hileman	University of Kansas
Brian C O'Meara	University of Tennessee-Knoxville

Germination, trait coevolution, and niche limits in changing environments

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=201

Dates: 2/5/2010 - 2/7/2010

PI

Kathleen Donohue

Institution

Duke University

CoPI

Rafael F Rubio de Casas

Duke University

Participants

Kathleen Donohue	Duke University
Kent Bradford	University of California-Davis
Susan Kalisz	University of Pittsburgh
Amity Wilczek	Brown University
Josh R Auld	NESCent
Jeannine Cavender-Bares	University of Minnesota
Charlie Willis	Duke University
James Clark	Duke University
Johanna Schmitt	Brown University
Liana Burghardt	Duke University
Lawrence Venable	University of Arizona
Rafael F Rubio de Casas	Duke University
Xavier Morin	European Institute of Innovation and Technology
Carol Baskin	University of Kentucky
Jessica Metcalf	Princeton University

Grass phylogeny working group ii: inferring the complex history of c4 photosynthesis in grasses

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=202

Dates: 3/8/2010 - 3/10/2010

PI

Erika J Edwards

Institution

Brown University

CoPI

Stephen Smith
Nicolas Salamin

NESCent
University of Lausanne

Participants

Erika J Edwards	Brown University
Stephen Smith	NESCent
Pascal-Antoine Christin	Brown University
Elizabeth Kellogg	University of Missouri-St. Louis
Guillaume Besnard	Imperial College
Khidir Hilu	Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
J. Travis Columbus	Rancho Santa Ana Botanic Garden
Melvin Duvall	Northern Illinois University
Sandra Aliscioni	University of Buenos Aires
Nigel Barker	Rhodes University
Colin P Osborne	University of Sheffield
Fernando Zuloaga	Instituto de Botanica Darwinion
Osvaldo Morrone	Instituto de Botanica Darwinion
Liliana M. Giussani	Instituto de Botanica Darwinion-CONICET
Trevor Hodkinson	Trinity College
Nicolas Salamin	Universite de Lausanne

Genetic monitoring: development of tools for conservation and management

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=31

Dates: 3/15/2010 - 3/19/2010

PI

Fred Allendorf

Institution

University of Montana-Missoula

CoPI

Michael Schwartz

Rocky Mountain Research Station

Participants

Fred Allendorf	University of Montana-Missoula
Christina Vojta	USDA Forest Service
Jeffrey Stetz	University of Montana
Ruth Shortbull	University of Montana
Michael Schwartz	USDA Forest Service
Kevin McKelvey	USDA Forest Service
Jennifer Jackson	Oregon State University
Dave Gregovich	Southwest Fisheries Science Center
Michael Hansen	University of Aarhus
Katherine Kendall	US Geological Survey Glacier Field Station
David Tallmon	University of Alaska-Southeast
Nils Ryman	Stockholm University
Maile Neel	University of Maryland-College Park (MD)
Robin Waples	Northwest Fisheries Science Center
Don Waller	University of Wisconsin-Madison
Linda Laikre	Stockholm University
Isabelle Olivieri	Universite de Montpellier II

Building tools for emerging model systems in development, evolution, and ecology

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=91

Dates: 3/26/2010 - 3/27/2010

PI

Elena M Kramer

Institution

Harvard University

CoPI

Participants

Antónia Monteiro
David Clements
Mike Shapiro
Bob Freeman
Todd Vision
Cassandra Extavour
Andrew Groover
Thom Sanger
Vladimir Gapeyev
Yuichiro Suzuki
Gregory Davis
John Willis
Susan Renn

Yale University
University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
University of Utah
Harvard Medical School
University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Harvard University
University of California-Davis
Harvard University
NESCent
Wellesley College
Bryn Mawr College
Duke University
Reed College

An integrative evolutionary approach to examine sexual selection as a mechanism of speciation

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=194

Dates: 3/27/2010 - 3/28/2010

PI

Rebecca Safran

Institution

University of Colorado

CoPI

Albert Uy

Syracuse University

Participants

Rebecca Safran
Albert Uy
Maria R Servedio
Alicia Frame
David Gray
Laurel Symes
Dustin Rubenstein
Eileen Hebets
Rafael Rodriguez
Patrik Nosil
Michael Kopp
Jenny Boughman
Sander Van Doorn
Tamra Mendelson

University of Colorado
Syracuse University
University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
California State University-Northridge
Dartmouth College
Columbia University
University of Nebraska
University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee
University of Colorado
University of Vienna
Michigan State University
University of Berne
University of Maryland-Baltimore County

Communicating the relevance of human evolution

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=203

Dates: 4/9/2010 - 4/11/2010

PI

Norman Johnson

Institution

University of Massachusetts-Amherst

CoPI

James J Smith
Louise Mead

Michigan State University
National Center for Science Education

Participants

Norman Johnson	University of Massachusetts-Amherst
Ann Demogines	University of Texas-Austin
Rebecca Jordan	Rutgers University
Briana Pobiner	Smithsonian Institution
James J Smith	Michigan State University
David Hillis	University of Texas-Austin
Louise Mead	National Center for Science Education
Chelsea Crawford	Monta Vista High School
T. Ryan Gregory	University of Guelph
Lauri Lebo	Independent Journalist
Robin A Smith	NESCent
Kristin Jenkins	NESCent
Jory P Weintraub	NESCent
John M Logsdon	University of Iowa
Randolph Nesse	University of Michigan-Ann Arbor

Evolution and development of polyphenisms: pathways to innovation and diversification

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=149

Dates: 5/12/2010 - 5/14/2010

<u>PI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
David Pfennig	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

<u>CoPI</u>	Indiana University-Bloomington
Armin Moczek	

<u>Participants</u>	
David Pfennig	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Ehab Abouheif	McGill University
Mary Jane West-Eberhard	Smithsonian Institute
Sonia E Sultan	Wesleyan University
Armin Moczek	University of Indiana
Ian Dworkin	Michigan State University
Tami Cruickshank	University of Indiana
Carl Schlichting	University of Connecticut
Emilie Snell-Rood	Indiana University-Bloomington
Matthew Wund	The College of New Jersey
Cris C Ledon-Rettig	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill
Susan Foster	Clark University

Measuring evolutionary change in modern human populations using cohort data

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=27

Dates: 5/21/2010 - 5/21/2010

<u>PI</u>	<u>Institution</u>
Diddahally Govindaraju	Boston University

<u>CoPI</u>	Cornell University
Andrew Clark	Yale University
Stephen Stearns	North Carolina State University
Trudy Mackay	

<u>Participants</u>	
Diddahally Govindaraju	Boston University
Charles J Goodnight	University of Vermont
Randolph Nesse	University of Michigan
Stephen Stearns	Yale University
Dorian Garrick	Iowa State University
Trudy Mackay	North Carolina State University
Douglas Ewbank	University of Pennsylvania
Anatoliy Yashin	Duke University
Shamil Sunyaev	Brigham & Women's Hospital and Harvard Medical School
Jacob Moorad	University of Georgia

Analysis and synthesis of physiologic data from the mammalian feeding apparatus

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=150

Dates: 5/20/2010 - 5/21/2010

PI

Christine Wall

Institution

Duke University

CoPI

Chris Vinyard
Medicine and Pharmacy
Susan Williams
Rebecca Z German

Northeastern Ohio Universities Colleges of
Ohio State University
Johns Hopkins University

Participants

Christine Wall
Chris Vinyard
Rebecca Z German
Vladimir Gapeyev
Xianhua Liu
Susan Williams

Duke University
Northeastern Ohio Universities Colleges of Medicine and
Johns Hopkins University
NESCent
NESCent
Ohio University

Floral assembly: quantifying the composition of a complex adaptive structure

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=90

Dates: 6/8/2010 - 6/10/2010

PI

Charles Fenster

Institution

University of Maryland-College Park

CoPI

Participants

Stacey D Smith
Stephen Smith
Lawrence Harder
Brian C O'Meara
Michael Alfaro
Lena C Hileman
Charles Fenster
William Scott Armbruster
Pamela K Diggle
Larry Hufford
Peter Stevens
Christopher Hardy
Amy Litt

Duke University
NESCent
University of Calgary
University of Tennessee-Knoxville
Washington State University
University of Kansas
University of Maryland-College Park
University of Portsmouth
University of Colorado
Washington State University
University of Missouri-St. Louis
Millersville State University
New York Botanical Garden

Montane diversity in space and time: linking evolutionary biology and macroecology

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=30

Dates: 6/14/2010 - 6/18/2010

PI

Ken Kozak

Institution

University of Minnesota-Twin Cities

CoPI

Catherine Graham
Carsten Rahbek

State University of New York-Stony Brook
University of Copenhagen

Participants

Catherine Graham	State University of New York-Stony Brook
Ken Kozak	University of Minnesota-Twin Cities
Kelly Zamudio	Cornell University
Rauri Bowie	University California-Berkeley
Craig Moritz	University California-Berkeley
Trina E Roberts	NESCent
Carlos Daniel Cadena	Universidad de los Andes
Jeremy VanDerWal	James Cook University
Ana Carnaval	The City College, City University of New York
Juan L Parra	State University of New York-Stony Brook
Juan C Santos	NESCent

Evolutionary shifts in vertebrate visual ecology and visual system morphology

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=192

Dates: 6/21/2010 - 6/24/2010

PI

Margaret Hall

Institution

Midwestern University

CoPI

Christopher Heesy
Andrew Iwaniuk
Neuroscience

Midwestern University
Canadian Centre for Behavioural

Participants

Margaret Hall
Thomas Lisney
Gillian Moritz
Christopher Heesy
Kara Yopak
Jason Kamilar
Nathaniel Dominy
Bret Moore
Eric Warrant
Esteban Fernandez-Juricic
Saul Nava
Shaun P. Collin
Ellis Loew

Midwestern University
University of Alberta
Dartmouth College
Midwestern University
University of California, San Diego
Yale University
University of California, Santa Cruz
Purdue University
University of Lund, Sweden
Purdue University
Harvard University
University of Western Australia, Australia
Cornell University

Software for bayesian evolutionary analysis by sampling trees

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=191

Dates: 6/30/2010 - 7/2/2010

PI

Alexei Drummond

Institution

University of Auckland

CoPI

Andrew Rambaut
Marc Suchard

University of Edinburgh
University of California-Los Angeles

Participants

Alexei Drummond
Mark Holder
Julia Palacios Roman
David L Swofford
Alexander Alekseyenko
Jeff Thorne
Peter Beerli
Andrew Rambaut
Daniel Ayers
Aaron Darling
Marc Suchard
Benjamin D Redelings

University of Auckland
Kansas University
University of Washington
Duke University and NESCent
New York University School of Medicine (New York, NY)
North Carolina State University
Florida State University
University of Edinburgh
University of Maryland-College Park
University of California-Davis
University of California-Los Angeles
NESCent

Integrating evolutionary theory with behavioral economics

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=219

Dates: 8/27/2010 - 8/28/2010

PI

Institution

CoPI

David Wilson	Binghamton University
John Gowdy	Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Participants

David Wilson	Binghamton University
Janet Landa	York University
David Rand	Harvard University
Robert Kurzban	University of Pennsylvania
Eva van den Broek	University of Amsterdam
Bruce Wexler	Yale University
Greg DeAngelo	Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute
Alex Rosenberg	Duke University
Daniel Nettle	Newcastle University
Robert Kadar	Binghamton University
Ulrich Witt	Max Planck Institute of Economics
Michael Cox	Indiana University
John Gowdy	Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute
Dennis Embry	PAXIS Institute

Analysis and synthesis of physiologic data from the mammalian feeding apparatus

URL: http://www.nescent.org/science/awards_summary.php?id=150

Dates: 8/30/2010 - 9/1/2010

PI

Institution

Christine Wall	Duke University
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CoPI

Chris Vinyard	Northeastern Ohio Universities Colleges of
Medicine and Pharmacy	
Susan Williams	Ohio State University
Rebecca Z German	Johns Hopkins University

Participants

Chris Vinyard	Northeastern Ohio Universities Colleges of Medicine and :
Christine Wall	Duke University
Rebecca Z German	Johns Hopkins University
Susan Williams	Ohio University
Jose Iriarte-Diaz	University of Chicago
Kathleen K Smith	Duke University
Vladimir Gapeyev	NESCent
Xianhua Liu	NESCent
Alfred W Crompton	Harvard University
Callum Ross	University of Chicago
Geerling EJ Langenbach	ACTA
Anthony Herrel	Museum national d'Histoire naturelle
Susan W. Herring	University of Washington
Frits De Vree	University of Antwerp
Maxx Toler	Duke University
Stephane Montuelle	Ohio University
Jillian Davis	Ohio University
Robert Druzinsky	University of Illinois (Chicago)
Alison Doherty	NEOUCOM
Bill Hylander	Duke University
Allan Thexton	King's College London

Appendix G: Publications From NESCent Supported Projects in Year 6

Publications

Catalysis Meeting	
Erika J Edwards Colin P Osborne Caroline A E Stromberg	Edwards, E. and S. Smith (2010). "Phylogenetic analyses reveal the shady history of C4 grasses" Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences.
Roy Plotnick	Plotnick, R. E., S.Q. Dornbos, and J. Chen 2010 Information landscapes and sensory ecology of the Cambrian Radiation. <i>Paleobiology</i> 36: 303-317
Cynthia M Beall Peter Robbins	Beall et al. 2010 Natural selection on EPAS1 (HIF2-alpha) associated with low hemoglobin concentration in Tibetan highlanders. <i>PNAS</i> 107:11459-11464
Massimo Pigliucci Christina L Richards Oliver Bossdorf	Christina L. Richards, Oliver Bossdorf and Massimo Pigliucci. 2010, What Role Does Heritable Epigenetic Variation Play in Phenotypic Evolution?, <i>BioScience</i> , volume 60, issue 3, pp. 232-237
Long-term Sabbatical	
Douglas Eernisse	Eernisse, D., M. Strathmann and R. Strathmann. 2010. <i>Henricia pumila</i> sp. nov.: A brooding seastar (Asteroidea) from the coastal northeastern Pacific. <i>Zootaxa</i> 2329: 22-36.
Michael S Rosenberg	Rosenberg, M.S. 2010. A Generalized Formula for Converting Chi-Square Tests to Effect Sizes for Meta-Analysis. <i>PLoS ONE</i> 5(4):e10059.
James H Hunt	James H. Hunt, Florian Wolschin, Michael T. Henshaw, Thomas C. Newman, Amy L. Toth, and Gro V. Amdam. 2010, Differential Gene Expression and Protein Abundance Evince Ontogenetic Bias toward Castes in a Primitively Eusocial Wasp, <i>PLoS ONE</i> , volume 5, issue 5, pp. e10674
Elizabeth Lacey	Elizabeth P. Lacey, Mary E. Lovin, Scott J. Richter and Dean A. Herington. 2010, Floral Reflectance, Color, and Thermoregulation: What Really Explains Geographic Variation in Thermal Acclimation Ability of Ectotherms?, <i>The American Naturalist</i> , volume 175, issue 3, pp. 335-349
Michael S Rosenberg	Manel, S., Joost, S., Epperson, B.K., Holderegger, R., Storfer, A., Rosenberg, M.S., Scribner, K., Bonin, A. & Fortin, M.-J. (2010) Perspectives on the use of landscape genetics to detect genetic adaptive variation in the field. <i>Molecular Ecology</i> , 19, 3760-3772.
Michael S Rosenberg	Epperson, B.K., McRae, B.H., Scribner, K., Cushman, S.A., Rosenberg, M.S., Fortin, M.-J., James, P.M.A., Murphy, M., Manel, S., Legendre, P. & Dale, M.R.T. (2010) Utility of computer simulations in landscape genetics. <i>Molecular Ecology</i> , 19, 3549-3564.
Michael S Rosenberg	Anderson, C.D., Epperson, B.K., Fortin, M.-J., Holderegger, R., James, P., Rosenberg, M.S., Scribner, K.T. & Spear, S. (2010) Considering spatial and temporal scale in landscape-genetic studies of gene flow. <i>Molecular Ecology</i> , 19, 3565-3575.
Postdoctoral Fellow	
Stephen Smith	Edwards, E. and S. Smith (2010). "Phylogenetic analyses reveal the shady history of C4 grasses." Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences.
Josh R Auld	Auld, J. R., and R. A. Relyea. 2010. Life-history plasticity and inbreeding depression under mate limitation and predation risk: cumulative lifetime fitness dissected with a life table response experiment. <i>Evolutionary Ecology</i> .

Liam J Revell	Revell, L. J., D. L. Mahler, J. R. Sweeney, M. Sobotka, V. E. Fancher, and J. B. Losos. 2010. Nonlinear selection and the evolution of variances and covariances for continuous characters in an anole. <i>Journal of Evolutionary Biology</i> 23: 407-421.
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Liam J Revell	Johnson, M. A., L. J. Revell, and J. B. Losos. 2010. Behavioral convergence and adaptive radiation: Effects of habitat use on territorial behavior in <i>Anolis</i> lizards. <i>Evolution</i> 64: 1151-1159.
Liam J Revell	Lindenfors, P., L. J. Revell, and C. L. Nunn. 2010. Sexual dimorphism in primate aerobic capacity: A phylogenetic test. <i>Journal of Evolutionary Biology</i> 23: 1183-1194.
Carlos A. Botero	Elias, DO, Botero, CA, Andrade MCB, Mason AC and MM Kasumovic. 2010. High resource valuation fuels "desperado" fighting tactics in female jumping spiders. <i>Behavioral Ecology</i>
Josh R Auld	Auld, J. R., and R. A. Relyea. 2010. Inbreeding depression in adaptive plasticity under predation risk in a freshwater snail. <i>Biology Letters</i> 6:222-224.
Julie A Meachen-Samuels	Meachen-Samuels, J.A. and Van Valkenburgh, B. 2010. Radiographs Reveal Exceptional Forelimb Strength in the Sabertooth Cat, <i>Smilodon fatalis</i> . <i>PLoS ONE</i> 5: e11412.
Josh R Auld	Anthes, N., P. David, J. R. Auld, J. N. A. Hoffer, P. Jarne, J. M. Koene, H. Kokko, M. C. Lorenzi, B. Pelissie, D. Sprenger, A. Staikou, and L. Scharer. 2010. Bateman gradients in hermaphrodites: An extended approach to quantify sexual selection. <i>American Naturalist</i> .
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Trina E Roberts	Roberts, T.E., T.R.B. Davenport, K.B.P. Hildebrandt, T. Jones, W.T. Stanley, E.J. Sargis, and L.E. Olson. 2010. The biogeography of introgression in the critically endangered African monkey <i>Rungwecebus kipunji</i> . <i>Biology Letters</i> 6(2): 233-237.
David Kidd	Brian Sidlauskas, Ganeshkumar Ganapathy, Einat Hazkani-Covo, Kristin P. Jenkins, Hilmar Lapp, Lauren W. McCall, Samantha Price, Ryan Scherle, Paula A. Spaeth and David M. Kidd. 2010, Linking Big: The continuing promise of evolutionary synthesis. <i>Evolution</i> , volume 64, issue 4, pp. 871-880
Brian L. Sidlauskas	Harmon LJ, Losos JB, Jonathan Davies T, Gillespie R, Gittleman JL, Bryan Jennings W, Kozak K, McPeck MA, Moreno-Roark F, Near TJ, Purvis A, Ricklefs RE, Schluter D, Schulte li J, Seehausen O, Sidlauskas B, Torres-Carvajal O, Weir J, Mooers A (2010) Early bursts of body size and shape evolution are rare in comparative data. <i>Evolution</i>
Einat Hazkani-Covo	Einat Hazkani-Covo, Raymond M. Zeller, William Martin and Harmit S. Malik. 2010, Molecular Poltergeists: Mitochondrial DNA Copies (numts) in Sequenced Nuclear Genomes, <i>PLoS Genetics</i> , volume 6, issue 2, pp. e1000834
Julie A Meachen-Samuels	J. A. Meachen-Samuels and W. J. Binder. 2010, Sexual dimorphism and ontogenetic growth in the American lion and sabertoothed cat from Rancho La Brea, <i>Journal of Zoology</i> , volume 280, issue 3, pp. 271-279
Julie A Meachen-Samuels	Meachen-Samuels, J. (2010) Comparative scaling of humeral crosssections of felids and canids using radiographic images. <i>Journal of Mammalian Evolution</i> 17:193-209.
Eric Schuettpelez	Korall, P., E. Schuettpelez, et al. (2010) Abrupt deceleration of molecular evolution linked to the origin of arborescence in ferns. <i>Evolution</i> .

Eric Schuettpelz	Pryer, K., E. Schuettpelz, et al. (2010) DNA barcoding exposes a case of mistaken identity in the fern horticultural trade. <i>Molecular Ecology Resources</i>
Samantha Price	Slater, S. Price, et al. (2010) Diversity versus disparity and the radiation of modern cetaceans. <i>Proceedings of the Royal Society B</i> .
Short-term Visitor	
Claire Williams	Williams, C. G. (2010). Long-distance pine pollen still germinates after meso-scale dispersal. <i>American Journal of Botany</i> 97(5)
Roy Plotnick	Andrew C. Scott, Fabien Kenig, Roy E. Plotnick, Ian J. Glasspool, William G. Chaloner and Cortland F. Eble. 2010, Evidence of multiple late Bashkirian to early Moscovian (Pennsylvanian) fire events preserved in contemporaneous cave fills, <i>Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology</i> , volume 291, issue 1-2, pp. 72-84
Travis Ingram	Ingram, T. (2010) Speciation along a depth gradient in a marine adaptive radiation
Working Group	
David Pfennig Armin Moczek	Pfennig, D. W., Wund, M. A., Snell-Rood, E. C., Cruickshank, T., Schlichting, C. D., & Moczek, A. P. Phenotypic plasticity's impacts on diversification and speciation. <i>Trends in Ecology and Evolution</i> (in press).
Joshua Tewksbury Lauren Buckley Robert Holt Michael Angilletta	Gilman et al. 2010 A framework for community interactions under climate change. <i>Trends in Ecology and Evolution</i> 25:325-331
Susan C Alberts Karen B Strier	Karen B. Strier, Jeanne Altmann, Diane K. Brockman, Anne M. Bronikowski, Marina Cords, Linda M. Fedigan, Hilmar Lapp, Xianhua Liu, William F. Morris, Anne E. Pusey, Tara S. Stoinski and Susan C. Alberts. 2010, The Primate Life History Database: a unique shared ecological data resource, <i>Methods in Ecology and Evolution</i> , volume 1, issue 2, pp. 199-211
Susan Kalisz Mark Johnston	Christopher G. Eckert, Susan Kalisz, Monica A. Geber, Risa Sargent, Elizabeth Elle, Pierre-Olivier Cheptou, Carol Goodwillie, Mark O. Johnston, John K. Kelly and David A. Moeller. 2010, Plant mating systems in a changing world, <i>Trends in Ecology & Evolution</i> , volume 25, issue 1, pp. 35-43
Fred Allendorf Michael Schwartz	Laikre L. et al.. 2010, Neglect of Genetic Diversity in Implementation of the Convention on Biological Diversity, <i>Conservation Biology</i> , volume 24, issue 1, pp. 86-88
Alexei Drummond Marc Suchard Andrew Rambaut	P. F. Campos, E. Willerslev, A. Sher, L. Orlando, E. Axelsson, A. Tikhonov, K. Aaris-Sorensen, A. D. Greenwood, R.-D. Kahlke, P. Kosintsev, T. Krakhmalnaya, T. Kuznetsova, P. Lemey, R. MacPhee, C. A. Norris, K. Shepherd, M. A. Suchard, G. D. Zazula, B. Shapiro and M. T. P. Gilbert Ancient DNA analyses exclude humans as the driving force behind late Pleistocene musk ox (<i>Ovibos moschatus</i>) population dynamics, <i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences</i> , volume 107, issue 12, pp. 5675-5680
Andrew Rambaut Alexei Drummond Marc Suchard	S.N. Bennett, A.J. Drummond, D.D. Kapan, M.A. Suchard, J.L. Munoz-Jordan, O.G. Pybus, E.C. Holmes and D.J. Gubler 2010 Epidemic Dynamics Revealed in Dengue Evolution, <i>Molecular Biology and Evolution</i> , volume 27, issue 4, pp. 811-818
Marc Suchard Alexei Drummond Andrew Rambaut	E. W. Bloomquist and M. A. Suchard 2010 Unifying Vertical and Nonvertical Evolution: A Stochastic ARG-based Framework, <i>Systematic Biology</i> , volume 59, issue 1, pp. 27-41
Rafael F Rubio de Casas Kathleen Donohue	Donohue, K., R. Rubio de Casas, Liana Burghardt, Katherine Kovach, Charles Willis. 2010. Germination, post-germination adaptation, and species ecological ranges. <i>Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics</i> . In press for December Issue

Appendix H: Press Coverage of NESCent Science and Activities for Year 6

General

- **“Biologists merge methods, results from different disciplines to find new meaning in old data”** (*Eurekalert*) http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-01/nesc-bmm011110.php
- **“International researchers call out for support of ‘synthetic science’”** (*Atlanta Examiner*) <http://www.examiner.com/science-in-atlanta/international-researchers-call-out-for-support-of-synthetic-science>

Postdoctoral fellows

Josh Auld:

- **“Scared snails opt for single parenthood rather than wait for a mate”** (*Eurekalert*) http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-08/nesc-sso081610.php
- **“Scared snails opt for single parenthood rather than wait for a mate”** (*USA Today*) <http://content.usatoday.com/topics/article/Organizations/Schools/Duke+University/05BLeVx0NRffH/1>
- **“Scared snails opt for single parenthood rather than wait for a mate”** (*Dallas Morning News*) <http://topics.dallasnews.com/article/OfCa3iP30y3Hn>
- **“Fearful snail becomes better breeder”** (*LiveScience*) <http://www.livescience.com/animals/hermaphrodite-snails-100817.html>

Carlos Botero:

- **“Blueprint of the songbird genome”** (*BBC News*) <http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/science/nature/8597808.stm>
- **“Desperate female spiders fight by different rules”** (*Eurekalert*) http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-06/nesc-dfs060510.php
- **“Desperate female spiders fight by different rules”** (*U.S. News and World Report*) <http://www.usnews.com/science/articles/2010/06/08/desperate-female-spiders-fight-by-different-rules.html>

- **“Male spiders are all bark, female spiders fight to kill”** (*Wired Science*)
<http://www.wired.com/wiredscience/2010/06/female-spider-fights/>
- **“Mindset matters most in female spider fights”** (*NOVA*)
<http://www.pbs.org/wgbh/nova/insidenova/2010/06/mindset-not-muscle-determines-success-in-female-spider-fighting.html>

Julie Meachen-Samuels:

- **“Male sabertoothed cats were pussycats compared to macho lions”** (*EurekaAlert*)
http://www.eurekaalert.org/pub_releases/2009-11/du-msc110509.php
- **“Sabertooth just a pussycat next to feline kin”** (*The Durham Herald-Sun*)
http://www.heraldsun.com/pages/full_story_news_durham/push?article-Sabertooth+just+a+pussycat+next+to+feline+kin%20&id=4368855&instance=main_article
- **“Sabertoothed males were pussycats”** (*Duke University Office of News and Communications*) <http://news.duke.edu/2009/11/sabertooth.html>
- **“Q: How do you sex a Smilodon? (A: Very carefully)”** (*Laelaps Science Blog*)
http://scienceblogs.com/laelaps/2009/11/for_decades_after_its_discover.php
- **“Sabertooth tigers were relative pussycats”** (*Fox News*)
<http://www.foxnews.com/scitech/2009/11/18/sabertooth-tigers-relative-pussycats/>
- **“Study paints sabertooths as relative pussycats”** (*MSNBC News*)
http://www.msnbc.msn.com/id/34026719/ns/technology_and_science-science/
- **“Saber equality”** (*National Public Radio, Los Angeles affiliate*)
<http://www.scpr.org/programs/loh-down-on-science/2010/05/13/saber-equality/>
- **“Why you should never arm wrestle a saber-toothed tiger”** (*EurekaAlert*)
http://www.eurekaalert.org/pub_releases/2010-07/nesc-wys062210.php
- **“Sabre-tooth cats wrestled prey with powerful front legs”** (*Discover Magazine*)
<http://blogs.discovermagazine.com/notrocketscience/2010/07/02/pocket-science-2-1-billion-year-old-fossils-and-arm-wrestling-a-sabre-tooth-cat/>
- **“Saber-toothed cats strong-armed prey”** (*Science News*)
http://www.sciencenews.org/view/generic/id/60839/title/Saber-toothed_cats_strong-armed_pre

- **“The saber-toothed cat’s true secret: its super-strong arms”** (*Discover*)
<http://blogs.discovermagazine.com/80beats/2010/07/06/the-saber-toothed-cats-true-secret-its-super-strong-arms/>

- **“Saber-toothed cats also had powerful arms”** (*MSNBC*)
http://www.msnbc.msn.com/id/38068870/ns/technology_and_science-science/

- **“Saber-tooth tigers add powerful arms to their arsenal”** (*Science*)
<http://news.sciencemag.org/sciencenow/2010/07/scienceshot-saber-tooth-tigers-a.html>

Liam Revell:

- **“Competition puts the brakes on body evolution in island lizards”** (*Eurekalert*)
http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-06/nesc-cpt061710.php

- **“Lizard camouflage confuses males about gender”** (*Wired Magazine*)
<http://www.wired.com/wiredscience/2010/07/lizard-camouflage-gender/#more-23411>

Trina Roberts:

- **“Africa’s rarest monkey had an intriguing sexual past, DNA study confirms”** (*Eurekalert*) http://www.eurekalert.org/emb_releases/2009-11/nesc-arm110909.php

- **“Africa's rarest monkey may have bred with baboons”** (*NatGeo News Watch, National Geographic*)
<http://blogs.nationalgeographic.com/blogs/news/chieffeditor/2009/11/africas-rarest-monkey-may-have.html>

- **“Monkey business: baboon may have been mate”** (*MSNBC News*)
http://www.msnbc.msn.com/id/33865208/ns/technology_and_science-science/

- **“Rare monkey interbred with baboons, study suggests”** (*LiveScience*)
<http://www.livescience.com/animals/091111-monkey-mates-baboon.html>

Eric Schuettpelz:

- **“DNA barcoding exposes fake ferns in international plant trade”** (*Eurekalert*)
http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-05/du-dbe050410.php

- **“DNA barcodes could protect plants”** (*The Raleigh News and Observer*) <http://www.newsobserver.com/2010/05/17/485775/science-briefs.html>
- **“Protecting plants through DNA testing”** (*The Charlotte Observer*) <http://www.charlotteobserver.com/2010/05/17/1440238/science-briefs.html>
- **“DNA barcodes expose fake ferns”** (*Duke News Office*) <http://news.duke.edu/2010/05/barcode.html>
- **“DNA barcode exposes 'fake' ferns for sale”** (*Futurity*) <http://futurity.org/science-technology/dna-barcode-exposes-fake-ferns-for-sale/>

Stephen Smith:

- **“Molecular study could push back angiosperm origins”** (*Eurekalert*) http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-03/nesc-msc031210.php
- **“Stephen Smith: the botanist hacker”** (*The Scientist*) <http://www.the-scientist.com/article/display/57180/>

Gregor Yanega:

- **“Hummingbirds: Magic in the Air”** (*Nature, PBS*) <http://www.pbs.org/wnet/nature/episodes/hummingbirds-magic-in-the-air/video-expert-hunters/5442/>

Catalysis meetings and working groups:

Erika Edwards et al.: Toward a new synthesis of the evolutionary history and ecology of C4 grasses

- **“Drier weather 30 million years ago may have led to grass evolution”** (*USA Today*) <http://content.usatoday.com/communities/sciencefair/post/2010/02/drier-weather-30-million-years-ago-may-have-led-to-grass-evolution/1>

Cynthia Beall and Peter Robbins: Human evolution and adaptation to high-altitude hypoxia

- **“Scientists uncover the genetic secrets that allow Tibetans to thrive in thin air”** (*Eurekalert*) http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-06/nesc-sut060510.php

- **“Tibetans carry unique gene to combat mountain sickness”** (*Discovery News*)
<http://news.discovery.com/human/tibetans-carry-unique-gene-to-combat-mountain-sickness.html>
- **“Tibetan gene find may help patients in intensive care”** (*Irish Times*)
<http://www.irishtimes.com/newspaper/ireland/2010/0609/1224272124849.html>
- **“Scientists cite fastest instance of human evolution yet”** (*New York Times*)
<http://www.nytimes.com/2010/07/02/science/02tibet.html>

Visiting scholars

Jim Hunt:

- **“The making of a queen: Road to royalty begins early in paper wasps”** (*EurekaAlert*)
http://www.eurekaalert.org/pub_releases/2010-05/nesc-tmo051910.php
- **“How does a wasp become a queen?”** (*Life's Little Mysteries*)
<http://www.lifeslittlemysteries.com/how-does-a-wasp-become-queen--0942/>
- **“Scientists square off on evolutionary value of helping relatives** (*The New York Times*)
<http://www.nytimes.com/2010/08/31/science/31social.html>

Claire Williams:

- **“Gone with the wind: Far-flung pine pollen still potent miles from the tree”** (*EurekaAlert*) http://www.eurekaalert.org/pub_releases/2010-04/nesc-gwt040310.php
- **“Pine pollen gets flight miles”** (*Science News*)
http://www.sciencenews.org/view/generic/id/58360/title/Pine_pollen_gets_flight_mile_s
- **“Pollen reaches record levels”** (*News and Observer*)
<http://www.newsobserver.com/2010/04/08/426997/pollen-reaches-record-levels.html>
- **“Local researchers: Pine pollen pervasive”** (*The Herald-Sun*)
http://www.heraldsun.com/view/full_story_news_durham/6987898/article-Local-researchers--Pine-pollen-pervasive?instance=main_article
- **“Loblolly pine pollen is everywhere”** (*Salisbury Post*)
<http://www.salisburypost.com/Health/040710-WEB-pine-pollen>

NESCent leadership and staff:

Allen Rodrigo:

- **“Penguin males with steady pitch make better parents”** (*Eurekalert*)
http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-07/nesc-pmw0711110.php
- **“Fat daddy’s best – for penguins”** (*New Zealand Herald*)
http://www.nzherald.co.nz/environment/news/article.cfm?c_id=39&objectid=10659300
- **“Why penguins can pig out”** (*The Post and Courier*)
<http://www.postandcourier.com/news/2010/jul/23/why-penguins-can-pig-out/>
- **“Humans tested by the speed of cultural change”** (*The News and Observer*)
<http://www.newsobserver.com/2010/05/03/464430/humans-tested-by-the-speed-of.html>

Craig McClain:

- **“When the dinner bell rings for seafloor scavengers, larger animals get first dibs”** (*Eurekalert*) http://www.eurekalert.org/pub_releases/2010-04/nesc-wtd040510.php
- **“Paradox of dining in deep, wet mud”** (*Science News*)
http://www.sciencenews.org/view/generic/id/58558/title/Paradox_of_dining_in_deep_wet_mud
- **“Deep sea dibs: When it comes to the worm, the crab is always early”** (*Down to Earth Magazine*)
http://www.downtoearth.org.in/full6.asp?foldername=20100531&filename=sci&sec_id=12&sid=2
- **“Monster bug? It’s no joke!”** (*MSNBC*)
<http://cosmiclog.msnbc.msn.com/archive/2010/03/31/2253964.aspx>
- **“Monster of the deep: Shocked oil workers catch two-and-a-half-foot 'woodlouse'”** (*Daily Mail*)
<http://www.dailymail.co.uk/sciencetech/article-1263042/Monster-deep-Oil-workers-dredge-giant-cousin-woodlouse.html#ixzz0lwBNk3In>
- **“Monster from deep”** (*The Sun*)

<http://www.thesun.co.uk/sol/homepage/news/2917518/Monster-from-the-oil-lagoon.html>

Appendix I: Active Projects in Year 6
 (Project Titles Are Hyperlinks)

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
Catalysis Meeting				
David Wilson	State University of New York-Binghamton	The nature of regulation: how evolutionary theory can inform the regulation of large-scale human social interactions	6/1/2009	5/31/2010
Alan Jones Jotun Hein Etsuko Moriyama Joe Thornton	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill Oxford University University of Nebraska-Lincoln University of Oregon	Evolution of g protein coupled signaling: lineages, constraints, and tempo	11/1/2009	10/31/2010
Jessica Metcalf 2 Rob Guralnick Alan Cooper	University of Adelaide University of Colorado University of Adelaide	Integrating datasets to investigate megafaunal extinction in the late quaternary	11/1/2009	10/31/2010
Richard Moore Tia-Lynn Ashman	Miami University-Oxford University of Pittsburgh	Emergence of gender and sex chromosomes: evolutionary insights from a diversity of taxa	5/1/2010	4/30/2011
James H Hunt	North Carolina State University	Evolution of insect sociality: an integrative modeling approach	4/1/2010	3/31/2011
Greger Larson Dolores Piperno Michael Purugganan Dorian Fuller Robin Allaby	Durham University National Museum of Natural History New York University University College-London University of Warwick	Domestication as an evolutionary phenomenon: expanding the synthesis	4/1/2010	3/31/2011
Sarah Reece Nick Savill Andrew Read Nicole Mideo	Institutes of Evolution, Immunology and Infection Research University of Edinburgh Pennsylvania State University University of Edinburgh	Evolution of infectious diseases: integrating empirical and modelling approaches	5/1/2010	4/30/2011
Graduate Fellow				
Bret Moore	Purdue University	Do retinal specializations reflect ecology? an evolutionary perspective.	8/23/2010	12/10/2010
Paul Durst	Duke University	Evaluating patterns and trends in insular body size evolution	8/23/2010	12/10/2010
Sarah Seiter	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill	Distinguishing trait value and trait plasticity in the evolution of reaction norms	8/23/2010	12/10/2010
Nimrod D Rubinstein	Tel-Aviv University (ISRAEL)	Detection of clade-specific accelerations and decelerations in gene evolutionary rates	9/20/2010	12/10/2010
Luke Mahler	Harvard University	Improving and testing ecological models of phenotypic diversification	9/1/2010	12/10/2010

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
Long-term Sabbatical				
James H Hunt	North Carolina State University	The evolution of sociality	9/1/2009	2/28/2010
Michael S Rosenberg	Arizona State University	Geography, phylogeny, and population: an evolutionary synthesis	9/1/2009	4/30/2010
John M Logsdon	University of Iowa	Sex, cells: an evolutionary inquiry into sexual reproduction	11/1/2009	7/31/2010
James H Hunt	North Carolina State University	The origins of arthropod sociality	3/1/2010	7/31/2010
Armin Moczek	Indiana University-Bloomington	The nature of nurture: how environmental and genetic information interact to shape development and evolution	9/1/2010	8/31/2011
Dorothee Huchon	Tel-Aviv University	Current view of rodent phylogenetic relationships	9/1/2010	8/31/2011
Tal Pupko	Tel-Aviv University	Evolutionary models accounting for multi-layer selection pressures	9/1/2010	8/31/2011

Postdoctoral Fellow				
Josh R Auld	NESCent	Evaluating the effects of inbreeding on dispersal	10/1/2009	9/30/2011
Carlos A. Botero	NESCent	Evolution of conventional signals: from individuals to populations and back	1/1/2009	12/31/2010
Marc J. Lajeunesse	NESCent	Meta-analysis and the comparative phylogenetic method	10/1/2008	9/30/2011
Trina E Roberts	NESCent	Sticky tips and misplaced roots: is there a bias in intraspecific phylogenetics?	8/1/2008	7/31/2011
Stephen Smith	NESCent	Integrating species distribution modeling and phylogenetics	10/1/2008	5/31/2010
Julie A Meachen-Samuels	NESCent	Competition, guild structure and evolution in the carnivora	8/1/2009	7/31/2011
Benjamin D Redelings	NESCent	Improved probabilistic models of insertion/deletion for phylogenetic inference	9/1/2009	8/31/2011
Liam J Revell	NESCent	Process and pattern in the phylogenetic analysis of comparative data	8/1/2009	7/31/2011
Juan C Santos	NESCent	Multivariate evolutionary analysis: integrating structural equation modeling and phylogenetics	10/1/2009	9/30/2011
Eric Schuettelpelz	NESCent	A phylogenetic approach to understanding the evolution of the earth's biomes	8/1/2009	7/31/2011

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
Gregor Yanega	NESCent	A comparative phylogenetic approach to the study of insular avian phenotypes	8/1/2009	7/30/2011
Peter Unmack	NESCent	A gis based approach to a priori prediction in aquatic biogeography.	8/1/2010	7/31/2012
Jenny L McGuire	NESCent	Examining paleontological extinction patterns to predict modern extinction vulnerability	9/1/2010	8/31/2012
Jennifer Verdolin	NESCent	Integrating behavioral syndromes into social networks: optimal distribution of phenotypes and group stability.	9/1/2010	8/31/2012
Clinton Francis	NESCent	Acoustic signal space conservatism: a framework for signal flexibility in noise	9/1/2010	8/31/2012
Rafael F Rubio de Casas	NESCent	Dispersal evolution in the angiosperms: the origin of heterocarpy	5/1/2010	4/30/2012

Short-term Visitor				
Roy Plotnick	University of Illinois	Movement paleoecology, trace fossils, and the evolution of behavior	1/16/2010	4/17/2010
Lennart Olsson	Jena University	The origin of evolutionary novelties in amphibian head development	4/15/2010	6/15/2010
Frans Plooi	International Research-institute on Infant Studies	Translation of field notes for developmental study of chimpanzee vocal communication	3/22/2010	4/22/2010
Claire Williams	Forest History Society	Domesticating forest carbon: a synthesis on forest adaptation to climate change	2/22/2010	5/17/2010
Shane Lavery	University of Auckland	Connectivity of new zealand coastal marine communities: a synthesis of datasets	5/10/2010	7/2/2010
Samantha Price	UC Davis	Evolution of mammalian dietary strategies and the importance of omnivory	8/14/2010	8/27/2010
Samantha Hopkins	University of Oregon	Evolution of mammalian dietary strategies and the importance of omnivory	8/14/2010	8/27/2010
Luke Mahler	Harvard University	New tools for investigating replicated adaptive radiation	7/18/2010	8/11/2010
Howard A Ross	University of Auckland (NEW ZEALAND)	Species delimitation using networks	10/18/2010	10/29/2010
Vincent Moulton	University of East Anglia (UNITED KINGDOM)	New applications of phylogenetic combinatorics	8/16/2010	8/27/2010
Katharina Huber	University of East Anglia	New applications of phylogenetic combinatorics	8/16/2010	8/27/2010

Name	Institution	Project Title	Start Date	End Date
Matina Kalcounis-Rüppell Maarten Vonhof Leslie Rissler	UNC Greensboro Western Michigan University University of Alabama	Potential for peripheral populations to mitigate core extinctions: bats and white nose syndrome.	10/1/2010	12/31/2010
Roi Dor	Cornell University (Ithaca,NY)	Applying new phylogenetic comparative methods to analyze character evolution in swallows	8/30/2010	9/5/2010

Working Group				
Charles Fenster William Scott Armbruster	University of Maryland-University College University of Alaska-Fairbanks	Floral assembly: quantifying the composition of a complex adaptive structure	3/1/2008	3/1/2010
Scott Hodges Elena M Kramer Hopi E Hoekstra	University of California-Santa Barbara Harvard University Harvard University	Building tools for emerging model systems in development, evolution, and ecology	3/1/2008	2/28/2010
David Pfennig Armin Moczek	University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill Indiana University-Bloomington	Evolution and development of polyphenisms: pathways to innovation and diversification	6/27/2008	6/26/2010
Christine Wall Chris Vinyard Susan Williams Rebecca Z German	Duke University Northeastern Ohio Universities Colleges of Medicine and Pharmacy Ohio State University Johns Hopkins University	Analysis and synthesis of physiologic data from the mammalian feeding apparatus	6/27/2008	6/26/2010
Alexei Drummond Marc Suchard Andrew Rambaut	University of Auckland University of California-Los Angeles University of Edinburgh	Software for bayesian evolutionary analysis by sampling trees	6/1/2009	3/31/2011
Margaret Hall Andrew Iwaniuk Christopher Heesy	Midwestern University Canadian Centre for Behavioural Neuroscience Midwestern University	Evolutionary shifts in vertebrate visual ecology and visual system morphology	6/1/2009	3/31/2011
Courtney Murren Carl Schlichting	College of Charleston University of Connecticut	Costs of phenotypic plasticity and adaptation to novel environments	6/1/2009	3/31/2011
Rebecca Safran Albert Uy	University of Colorado Syracuse University	An integrative evolutionary approach to examine sexual selection as a mechanism of speciation	6/1/2009	3/31/2011
Kathleen Donohue Rafael F Rubio de Casas	Duke University Duke University	Germination, trait coevolution, and niche limits in changing environments	11/1/2009	10/31/2011
Erika J Edwards Nicolas Salamin Stephen Smith	Brown University University of Lausanne NESCent	Grass phylogeny working group ii: inferring the complex history of c4 photosynthesis in grasses	11/1/2009	10/31/2011
Norman Johnson James J Smith Louise Mead	University of Massachusetts-Amherst Michigan State University National Center for Science Education	Communicating the relevance of human evolution	11/1/2009	10/31/2011
David Wilson John Gowdy	Binghamton University Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute	Integrating evolutionary theory with behavioral economics	5/1/2010	4/30/2012

Appendix J: Projects Supported In Year 6

(Project Titles Are Hyperlinks)

Catalysis Meeting	
Dorian Fuller Robin Allaby Dolores Piperno Michael Purugganan Greger Larson	Domestication as an evolutionary phenomenon: expanding the synthesis
Nicole Mideo Nick Savill Andrew Read Sarah Reece	Evolution of infectious diseases: integrating empirical and modelling approaches
James H Hunt	Evolution of insect sociality: an integrative modeling approach
Tia-Lynn Ashman Richard Moore	Emergence of gender and sex chromosomes: evolutionary insights from a diversity of taxa
Graduate Fellow	
Bret Moore	Do retinal specializations reflect ecology? an evolutionary perspective.
Paul Durst	Evaluating patterns and trends in insular body size evolution
Nimrod D Rubinstein	Detection of clade-specific accelerations and decelerations in gene evolutionary rates
Sarah Seiter	Distinguishing trait value and trait plasticity in the evolution of reaction norms
Luke Mahler	Improving and testing ecological models of phenotypic diversification
Long-term Sabbatical	
Armin Moczek	The nature of nurture: how environmental and genetic information interact to shape development and evolution
James H Hunt	The origins of arthropod sociality
Tal Pupko	Evolutionary models accounting for multi-layer selection pressures
Dorothee Huchon	Current view of rodent phylogenetic relationships
Postdoctoral Fellow	
Clinton Francis	Acoustic signal space conservatism: a framework for signal flexibility in noise
Jennifer Verdolin	Integrating behavioral syndromes into social networks: optimal distribution of phenotypes and group stability
Rafael F Rubio de Casas	Dispersal evolution in the angiosperms: the origin of heterocarpy
Jenny L McGuire	Examining paleontological extinction patterns to predict modern extinction vulnerability
Peter Unmack	A gis based approach to a priori prediction in aquatic biogeography.
Short-term Visitor	
Shane Lavery	Connectivity of new zealand coastal marine communities: a synthesis of datasets
Claire Williams	Domesticating forest carbon: a synthesis on forest adaptation to climate change
Howard A Ross	Species delimitation using networks
Luke Mahler	New tools for investigating replicated adaptive radiation
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Maarten Vonhof Leslie Rissler Matina Kalcounis-Rüppell	Potential for peripheral populations to mitigate core extinctions: bats and white nose syndrome.
Vincent Moulton Katharina Huber	New applications of phylogenetic combinatorics
Working Group	
John Gowdy David Wilson	Integrating evolutionary theory with behavioral economics